

24 June 2004

To: All Designated Officials
All Field Security Coordination Officers
All Security Focal Points

From: Diana Russler
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Subject: Security Risk Management

In view of the rapidly changing security environment in which organizations of the United Nations system must operate, UNSECOORD and DPKO together with other organizations have developed a new Security Risk Management process (SRM) to provide security officials in the field with a new tool to identify threats, determine risks associated with these threats and develop appropriate mitigating strategies to control activities. The new process is designed to enable the United Nations system to conduct its operations with the security and safety of staff as a high priority.

The Inter-Agency Security Management Network (IASMN) considered the SRM model at its meeting in May 2004 and recommended its immediate adoption as a tool to enable enhanced security management at the local, regional and Headquarters levels.

The IASMN has reiterated that the primary responsibility for the preparation of a country-specific SRM report rests with the Designated Official and Security Management Team. Accordingly, the IASMN has requested each Designated Official and Security Management Team to initiate the security management process and to identify areas of vulnerability in order to determine the measures necessary to mitigate risk. These measures should be incorporated into the country-specific Minimum Operating Security Standards (MOSS). The SRM must be submitted to UNSECOORD which will maintain oversight of the process. Designated Officials and Security Management Teams are requested to complete this process and submit the SRM report to UNSECOORD no later than 1 September 2004. Thereafter, the SRM, which is an ongoing cyclical exercise, must be maintained, reviewed and updated on a regular basis.

IASMN recognizes that, in some situations, organizations of the UN system are required to conduct their own specific programme-related threat and risk assessments. In such cases, IASMN expects that the organization-specific SRM report must be submitted to the Designated Official and Security Management Team for consideration.

Best regards.

cc. Ms. Bertini
Mr. Mengesha

SECURITY RISK MANAGEMENT

I. Introduction

1. Crime, war, terrorism, natural disasters and accidents represent security threats and challenges to United Nations system staff, security officers and decision-makers. With limited budgets and expanding operational demands, the assessment and management of the risk associated with these threats to the organizations of the United Nations and their staff members are critical to safe and effective operations.
2. Commercial companies, industries and State entities all use risk management as part of their efforts to mitigate the effects of possible adverse events. To implement effective, efficient and safe operations in hazardous environments, the United Nations system must do likewise.
3. The approach described below is a robust, effective process and methodology that has been developed specifically with United Nations field operations in mind. The Security Risk Management (SRM) process enables security officials to determine the threats they face, the levels of risk of each threat and to identify and implement appropriate mitigating factors in accordance with the programmatic needs of the organization.
4. In the past, the United Nations had often concentrated only on the threats and attempted to protect against all those threats, at times to the detriment of programme requirements. However, the SRM process now permits the assessment of the threats, determination of vulnerabilities, include programme needs and the analysis of the risk in terms of their impact and likelihood. This allows the organizations to be more proficient in identifying mitigation measures and more efficient in allocating security resources. In most cases, the result is the continuation of operations, safer working environments for staff and efficient and effective management of security funds and resources.

A. Scope

5. This document describes the SRM process to be implemented by the United Nations system. It provides a detailed description of each of the eight stages of the process and provides the user with a tool to undertake realistic security risk assessments as part of SRM.

B. Terminology

6. SRM is an analytical procedure that assists in assessing the likelihood of undesirable events that may affect United Nations system personnel, property, programmes and mandates, and supports the implementation of specific risk mitigation strategies to lower this likelihood by reducing the probability and impact of an undesirable event.
7. Prior to the introduction of SRM, the term 'Threat Assessment' was used as a generic description for the process used to determine levels of threat and subsequently identify United Nations system Security Phases. In SRM the term, 'Threat Assessment' is only one of the eight

stages within the process. Key terms referred to in this document are listed below. Other terms used within SRM are provided at Annex A.

- **Threat** – Any indication, action, circumstance or event that may cause harm or damage to the United Nations system, including its personnel.
- **Risk** - The probability or likelihood for harm or loss to the organizations’ personnel, equipment, facilities or reputation from the threats.
- **Vulnerability** – any weakness that can be exploited by a belligerent to gain access to an asset. Vulnerabilities can result from, but are not limited to, the following: building characteristics, equipment properties, personal behaviour, locations of people, equipment and buildings or operational and personnel practices.

II. Security Risk Management

8. The SRM process consists of eight stages: Programme Assessment, Threat Assessment, Vulnerability Assessment, Risk Analysis, Selection of Options, Decision Making, Implementation and Monitoring/Review.

9. The Threat, Vulnerability, and Programme Assessment stages incorporate the collection and deduction of relevant information. They provide the essential information required to determinate risk.

10. During the Risk Analysis stage, decisions are made based on the deductions provided from the assessments. This is the most critical stage as it is here that the level of risk, its acceptability, and the possible mitigation factors are determined.

11. The final four stages describe the selection of available options, decision-making, implementation of the selected options, and the review and monitoring of changes to the threats and vulnerabilities.

Diagram 1 – The Security Risk Management model

III. Stages of the SRM Process

12. Of the eight stages of the SRM process, the three ‘assessments’ may be considered in any order. However, it is usual to consider either the Threat Assessment or the Programme Assessment first. In so doing, many other factors from the other assessments will become clear.

13. A rating system is necessary when articulating the levels of risk, threat, impact and likelihood. In the SRM process, one- or two-word descriptors are used, and these may be generally linked to a numerical scale of 1 to 5. This rating system is described in more detail at each stage.

Diagram 2 – The Interaction of Threat, Programme and Vulnerability Assessments

A. Threat Assessment

14. The Threat Assessment provides both a general and specific view of the operating environment, together with the identification of those Threats that may impact on the United Nations and its operations. Considerable effort is required to obtain credible and accurate information when developing the Threat Assessment.

15. Threat Assessments do not provide an assessment of risk, but provide the information and deductions that are used within a Risk Analysis (see stage 4 below). It consists of two steps: Situational Analysis and Determination of Threats.

Diagram 3 – Steps within the Threat Assessment

- a. Step a. Situational Analysis. Information is gathered from a wide variety of sources, such as United Nations organizations, non-governmental organizations, diplomatic missions, the host government, security forces, local populations and the media. This information is grouped under several factors, namely Social, Economic, Political, Infrastructure, and Security Forces (see Annex B). The situational analysis is a detailed review of the complete operating, living and security environment.
- b. Step b. Determining Threats. All activities, circumstances, events, persons and actions that may have an adverse effect on United Nations system staff, facilities, or equipment, are considered in this step. Threats may be divided into four general types: (1) 'Perceived' threats - possible but no clear information (i.e., a threatening telephone call without known substance); (2) 'Actual' threats from known criminals, disgruntled individuals, weapons systems, prior attacks; (3) 'Direct' threats – those directed specifically at the United Nations system or its personnel, facilities or equipment such as the terrorist attacks similar to the Baghdad bomb attack on 19 August 2003; (4) 'Indirect' threats that may effect the United Nations (i.e., being caught in the wrong place at the wrong time).

B. Vulnerability Assessment

16. The Vulnerability Assessment identifies the strengths and weaknesses of the security arrangements in the environment in which the United Nations system conducts its activities. It consists of two steps: Determine Vulnerabilities and Determine Mitigating Factors.

Diagram 4 – Steps within the Vulnerability Assessment Stage

a. Step a. Determine Vulnerabilities. Vulnerability is our exposure to the threat; therefore, our vulnerabilities are the gaps or 'weaknesses' in existing security arrangements. They include such factors as poor perimeter fencing of compounds, ineffective security forces, an uncooperative or incapable host government, missions only able to be conducted by road, a lack of staff security training, a lack of reliable information on the threats, essential programmes necessarily conducted in the field, non-MOSS compliance and inexperienced staff. As 'weaknesses', the vulnerabilities are compared against the mitigating factors. It is important that this step be undertaken in detail so that all weaknesses are noted.

b. Step b. Determine Mitigating Factors. Mitigating factors are considered 'strengths' that may lessen the impact of a threat against the Organization. Examples may include full MOSS compliance, excellent response from an effective security force, well located and appointed UN House, body armour available to staff, good Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), use of a helicopter for some missions, comprehensive communications network and exercising the Security Plan. Mitigating factors are compared against the vulnerabilities, and will include the

security phase, as this is a regulatory system that has significant behavioural and psychological effect on the staff.

C. Programme Assessment

17. The Programme Assessment is an evaluation of the relevance, urgency, needs and implementation methodology of the United Nations system activities in a given environment. At the country level it is conducted by the country team (normally heads of agency) and is continually assessed against the threats, vulnerabilities and risks. The Programme Assessment continually links into other stages of the process. As relevant data is collated, it should be tabulated for reference during subsequent stages.

18. Non-exhaustive lists of questions, which can be used in the development of a Programme Assessment, are provided at Annex C.

D. Risk Analysis

19. Risk Analysis is a method of combining all the factors and deductions from the assessments and determining the possible *impact* (or consequences) on the Organization, together with the *likelihood* that the particular adverse event will occur. It is not possible to finalise a Risk Analysis until the threats, programmes and vulnerabilities have been assessed.

20. It is important to note that, even if the threat is significant and present, if the likelihood of it impacting on the United Nations system is negligible, and the impact is considered to be minor, then the risk must be low or perhaps even negligible.

Example:

The Threat Assessment indicates that car bombs are common weapons used in country X. The Vulnerability and Programme Assessments indicate that the UN has poor security arrangements but our presence is vital to country X. The UN House is located alongside a main road with lots of window glass. The Risk Analysis will determine the *likelihood* of such an attack and the *impact* on the Organization. In this example, the *impact* of a car bomb exploding near to the UN House will result in multiple deaths and injuries, and cancellation of UN activities. The *likelihood* is high as credible information provided from a reliable source indicates a group of people want to make the UN leave! Therefore, the level of risk is high/critical. At this level of risk, UN system security decision-makers (e.g., DO, SMT, etc.) would be justified in deciding to immediately deploy additional armed police guards, close all adjacent roads and install shatter resistant film (SRF) on all windows, which will reduce the impact and likelihood of an attack and, therefore, lower the risk. In addition, the decision-makers may have to relocate all staff to temporary, safer accommodation until UN system staff can return to the UN house.

21. Risk Analysis has two distinct steps.

Diagram 5 – Steps within the Risk Analysis

a. Step 1. Impact. The impact may include death or injury to staff, loss of equipment, loss of information, destruction of facilities, defamation to the Organization, loss of credibility and programme delays and/or cancellation. The expected impact may be determined from historical records of previous incidents or similar situations from other countries. A certain amount of impact will be clearly acceptable, such as minor delays in development programmes, loss of minor equipment and minor mental stress on staff; other types of impact will be unacceptable, as in the case of death, serious injury, destruction of facilities and cessation of emergency humanitarian programmes and operations. Definitions of the descriptors for impact are at Table 1.

Descriptor	Definitions
Negligible	The consequences may result in minor disruption to UN system activities.
Minor	The consequences may result in some minor injuries to staff; possible damage or some loss of equipment and facilities; and limited delays to activities.
Moderate	The consequences may result in injury to staff; some loss of equipment and facilities; and delays to activities.
Severe	The consequences result in severe injury to staff; significant loss of equipment and facilities; and major delays and possible cancellation of activities.
Critical	The consequences are catastrophic, resulting in death and severe injury to staff; major loss of equipment and facilities; and cancellation of activities.

Table 1 – Definitions of 'Impact' descriptors

b. Step 2. Likelihood. Statistics, experience and recent history are used when determining the likelihood of an adverse event. One- or two-word descriptors are used to rate the likelihood of an incident occurring. If the threat is credible and may cause significant loss to the UN system, but the likelihood of such an event is considered negligible, then the risk could be considered low or negligible. Definitions for the descriptors associated with likelihood are at Table 2.

Descriptor	Definitions
Unlikely	This event is considered as <u>not having a realistic probability</u> of occurring against the UN under the prevailing conditions, i.e., <u>monitor the situation closely</u> .
Moderately Likely	This event is considered <u>to have a reasonable probability</u> of occurring against the UN under the prevailing conditions. <u>Effort should be made</u> to reduce this probability, or the impact of the event occurring, i.e., <u>review security procedures and arrangements</u> .
Likely	This event is considered <u>to have a high probability</u> of occurring against the UN under the prevailing conditions. <u>Significant effort</u> is required to reduce this probability, or the impact of the event occurring, i.e., <u>review MOSS compliance and training</u> .
Very Likely	This event is considered <u>to have a very high probability</u> of occurring against the UN under the prevailing conditions. <u>Every available effort</u> is required to reduce this probability, or the impact of the event occurring, i.e., <u>relocate dependants or staff</u> .
Certain/Imminent	This event is considered to be imminent and will occur. The Organization must take immediate and extreme measures to protect itself, i.e., <u>evacuate to a safe haven</u> .

Table 2 – Definitions of 'Likelihood' descriptors

Practical Hint:

Determining the 'Likelihood' of an adverse event will often rely on the experience level of the UN security team, including the DO and SMT, but may utilize statistical and historical information. If an adversary has shown intent (or mind-set) to attack the United Nations, and has known capabilities, together with a history of such attacks, the likelihood is most probably 'Very Likely'.

E. Selecting Options

22. At this point of the process, decision-makers and security officials must determine what courses of action, or options, are possible to maintain the safety and security of the Organization, its staff and property. These options must be determined in light of the risks and the programme imperative established in the Programme Assessment. Some examples of options are: (1) Do nothing and continue under existing arrangements; (2) implement improved access control measures; (3) lease a helicopter for field missions; (4) employ armed guards; (5) postpone or cancel non-critical programmes and projects; (6) utilise implementing partners for all field programmes; (7) raise the security phase and reduce staff; or (8) evacuate. Many options may include significant funding, political and/or operational considerations, and each of these must be addressed in the preparation of the options to be considered.

23. It is necessary to ensure that the safety and security of United Nations system staff is a high priority when determining available options.

F. Make Decisions

24. This stage consists of two steps. This practical stage requires decisions to be made about priorities, logistical support, funding and timeframes. Programme pressures, financial limitations, contractor and host government delays, political ramifications and differing opinions make this stage extremely demanding. Correct decisions cannot be made without a concerted commitment to reduce risk and a complete understanding of the consequences of not reducing risk.

Diagram 6 – Steps within the Decision Making stage

- a. Step 1. Determine Priorities and Create a Timeframe. Not all elements of the selected option will be achieved at the same time, and priorities (i.e., for funding and construction) must be established. Moreover, time for implementation and completion of the selected options will be critical to reduce the risk to the Organization and its staff. Temporary risk reduction measures may be required whilst projects are being completed, for example, reduced frequency of road missions, delays in implementing projects, or even temporary relocation of staff.
- b. Step 2. Determine Funding and Resource Needs. The available financial resources are often less than what is needed to fund all selected options. Designated Officials, Security Management Teams, Field Security Coordination Officers and Area Security Coordinators (Risk Managers) should be aware of the cost-benefit of any option taken and prioritize them accordingly. Resources available may be of varying quality, including materials, technical

competence and confidentiality. Care must be taken to ensure the appropriate type and quantity of resources are made available in a timely manner.

G. Implementation

25. The Implementation stage may involve alterations to United Nations activities by canceling some projects, whilst initiating others. It may involve the purchase of equipment, training of staff or changes in personnel or security phases. Whatever options are selected, there must be a determination by decision-makers to implement those options as rapidly as called for by the risk assessment.

26. It is not sensible to conduct the first six stages of the security risk management process to only delay or reduce support for its implementation. Without this stage operating effectively, the entire security risk management process will fail. Therefore, once the decision is made, there must be a strong commitment for implementing the plan.

H. 'Review and Monitor'

27. The constant review and monitoring of the threat, vulnerabilities, programmes and risks are essential. The Review and Monitor stage is the last stage within the security risk management model and it is comprised of the following four steps:

Diagram 7 – Steps within the Review and Monitor stage

- a. Step 1. Lessons Learned. After each incident or activity, lessons must be recorded and acted upon. This may include changes in the type and way information is collected or assessed within the overall process, or incorporating previously un-noticed Vulnerabilities or Mitigating Factors. Lessons Learned must be monitored to ensure implementation.
- b. Step 2. Identify New Threats. New threats will continue to surface or existing threats will increase in severity. Therefore, new and updated information is critical to keep the security risk management process valid and effective.

- c. Step 3. Refine and Update All Assessments. This step ensures that levels of risk are constantly amended as the environment/situation changes. This is continuously accomplished using the original assessments.
- d. Step 4. Adjust Implementation Plan. When changes are identified, the implementation plans may need subsequent modification, and security officials must be prepared to constantly factor in new information to adjust their plan.

IV. Considerations and Deductions

28. Not all information collected will necessarily be relevant to security risk management. At each step of the security risk management process, information should be filtered by asking the question, “Is this piece of information relevant to our security?” If the information is relevant, a deduction should be made as to the action that should be taken. If the information is not relevant, it should not be considered further. This technique will assist in managing the volume of information being considered within the SRM process. It will also lead to a list of required actions to be addressed in the security plan.

Examples:

*Factor: The local Police Force are willing to assist the UN but their effectiveness is poor. *Is this relevant?*

Consideration 1: *Yes. We cannot expect the police to provide protection to UN staff. Is this relevant?*

Consideration 2: *Yes. Staff is vulnerable to robbery, theft or attack. Is this relevant?*

Deduction: *Yes. We need to establish an effective UN security guard force (potential Mitigating Factor).*

*Factor: The ambulance services are non-effective, though medical facilities are good. *Is this relevant?*

Consideration: *Yes. UN staff may suffer delays in medical care on mission. Is this relevant?*

Deduction: *Yes. Comprehensive First Aid kits and training are required for all Agencies.*

*Factor: Terrorists have recently used car bombs against international organizations. *Is this relevant?*

Consideration 1: *Yes. The UN may become a target. Is this relevant?*

Consideration 2: *Yes. There is no control over parking adjacent to the UN building. Is this relevant?*

Consideration 3: *Yes. A car bomb could be left 15 metres from the UN offices. Is this relevant?*

Deduction: *Yes. Shatter Resistant Film and access controls are required at all UN compounds.*

*Factor: There has been a reduction in tourism in the country over the past 6 months. *Is this relevant?*

Deduction: *No. Various governments for past 12 months have issued 'Travel Warnings'.*

V. Levels of Risk

29. The United Nations security management system uses one-word descriptors to describe levels of risk. Definitions of these descriptors are contained in Table 3. These general ratings provide guidance to mission leaders, DOs, SMTs, FSCOs and others involved in security decision-making. The risk level, and the capacity to mitigate this risk, has a significant bearing on the selection of the security phase at the country level and whether missions traveling to or within the country are approved.

Descriptor	Definitions
Negligible	There is little likelihood of harm to the operation. Operations generally continue with minimal interruption. This risk is usually acceptable.
Low	There may be harm to the Organization either through indirect or unintentional means. However, the likelihood and outcome of adverse events is unlikely to result in significant damage, injury or delay. This risk can typically be mitigated and therefore is generally acceptable.
Medium	There is significant concern for the well being and security of the Organization. The degree of harm, or the likelihood of the adverse event, is significant. Security officials must implement significant measures to ensure the security and safety of staff and the protection of the Organization. This risk is likely to be at the limit of acceptability.
High	There is considerable concern for the security and safety of staff and the Organization. The situation is often unpredictable, and likely to end in violence. Very specific and robust security measures must be in place before the Organization can safely operate. Typically only security or emergency tasks are undertaken in this environment. This risk is unacceptable in most situations.
Critical	The operating environment is extremely dangerous. Available risk mitigating factors have minimal positive effect or are ineffective. The probability of death, severe injury, total damage or failure is extreme. This risk is unacceptable except in extraordinary instances.

Table 3 – Definitions of ‘Level of Risk’ descriptors

VI. The Security Risk Assessment

30. The SRM process also enables a standardized, practical and flexible approach to the conduct and articulation of a ‘Security Risk Assessment (SRA)’. When conducting an SRA, the first five stages of the SRM are undertaken and recommendations are included.

31. The SRA is the most practical and most often used product of the SRM and can be conducted at the deep field, country and headquarters levels. In addition, it can be used, *inter alia*, for assessments of other activities, such as missions, determining whether or not to use armed escorts, selection of office facilities, determining security phases and establishing MORSS and MOSS requirements. Several Designated Officials have completed the Country Assessment for their duty station found at Example 3, and use this as a guide at every SMT meeting in reviewing the prevailing security situation at their duty station. Specifically, they look for key changes that impact on the security environment, and then adjust the assessment accordingly. This enables them to quickly review security phases, MOSS requirements and other security-related decisions and recommendations.

32. Almost all decisions of an SMT could be supported by an appropriate SRA. They may be written in a formal document or, in the case of a crisis or change of mission planning, jotted in a notebook. Regardless of the form in which it is presented, the SRA should follow the SRM model and always include recommendations for decision makers.

VII. Limitations of Using a Model in Security

33. It is important to note the SRM process has its own limitations. It does not seek to inhibit current practices or the use of other security management tools and/or instruments by security officers and decision makers. Rather, it provides a logical and standardized means to ensure all facets of threat and risk are incorporated into all aspects of United Nations system planning.

34. Use of a standardized process facilitates the work of UNSECOORD and senior management at the Headquarters level in supporting field requirements for additional security resources, in order to effectively implement its activities.

VIII. Conclusions

35. Security is a vital responsibility of all personnel, under the leadership and coordination of the Designated Official. While absolute security can never be guaranteed, threats and risks can be mitigated and vulnerabilities reduced once they have been identified and assessed. A formalized security risk management process is the key to accomplishing this vital task so as to enable the United Nations system to discharge its primary functions and mandates.

36. The SRM process outlined in this document is a practical process by which the complex issues surrounding security can be identified and assessed so as to arrive at comprehensive and focused preventative measures. The process, which is based on modern security risk management practices, will also produce solid rationale for the necessary expenditures on physical security measures, equipment, services or other security-related requirements.

37. Circumstances bearing on security continuously change. For this reason, the SRM process will become an integral part of total security management of the United Nations system. In this manner, all concerned can be assured of up-to-date, relevant, economically effective and comprehensive security planning.

Terminology

For the purpose of this document, the following definitions of key terms are used. These terms are the standard vocabulary used within the United Nations.

- **Risk** - The probability for harm or loss to the organizations of the UN system and their personnel from the threats.
- **Threat** – Any indication, action, circumstance or event that may cause harm or damage to the United Nations system, including its personnel, equipment and facilities.
- **Belligerent** – Any individual, group or organization which conducts activities, or has the intention and capability to conduct activities, detrimental to the organizations of the UN system.
- **Risk Management** – An analytical tool for assessing the likelihood of threats that may affect UN system personnel, missions and other assets, which supports implementation of specific risk mitigation strategies to lower the probability and/or impact of the identified threats.
- **Asset** – Any equipment, facility, material or information that has a positive value to the UN system. The asset may have value to a belligerent, as well as the UN system, although the nature and magnitude of those values may differ.
- **Impact** – The amount of loss or damage that can be expected, or may be expected, from an undesirable event affecting an asset. Loss may be monetary, but may also include operational effectiveness, credibility, political issues and morale, as well as other factors.
- **Monitoring** – The ongoing collection, analysis and dissemination of information relating to changes in the operational environment and the implementation of risk mitigation measures.
- **Mitigation measure** – Any action taken or physical equipment used to reduce or eliminate vulnerabilities. Mitigation measures may affect the threat (intent and/or capability) as well as an asset's value. The cost of a possible mitigation measure may be monetary but may also include non-monetary costs such as reduced operational effectiveness, adverse publicity, unfavourable working conditions and political consequences.
- **Risk Analysis** – The process of determining the likelihood of a belligerent successfully exploiting vulnerabilities and the resulting degree of impact on an asset. A risk analysis provides the basis for establishing priorities for the application of mitigation strategies.
- **Risk Mitigation** – The process of selecting, implementing and monitoring security mitigation measures and the operational environment to achieve an accepted level of risk.
- **Vulnerability** – Any weakness that can be exploited by a belligerent to gain access to an asset. Vulnerabilities can result from, but are not limited to, the following: building characteristics, equipment properties, personal behaviour, locations of people, equipment and buildings or operational and personnel practices.

UNSECOORD GUIDELINE FOR SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS

The Situational Analysis should include a wide range of information to ensure a detailed understanding of the operational environment. The following headings are a non-exhaustive list and may be expanded in accordance with the local situation.

- **Political**
 - Government activities affecting security
 - Parties and factions
 - Trade unions
 - Regional relationships
- **Economic**
 - Major industries
 - Employment
 - Wages
 - Inflation
 - Per capita income
 - Exchange rates
 - Black market activities
 - Cost of living
- **Social**
 - Composition of population
 - Influence of religion/religious groups
 - Influence of tribes/tribal traditions
 - Racial tensions
 - Civil conflict
 - Public health
- **Infrastructure**
 - Road networks
 - Airports
 - Ports
 - Railroads
 - Mass transportation
 - Electricity/Power system
 - Communications (internal and external)
 - Water supply
- **Security Forces – Military**
 - General composition
 - Stability of forces
 - Special units (bomb disposal)
 - Ability to defend the country
 - Populace attitude towards the military
- **Security Forces – Police**
 - General description – national, state, city police
 - Special police units (dog squad, counter-terrorism)
 - Ability to maintain law and order
 - Populace attitude towards the police

**QUESTIONS FOR USE IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF A PROGRAMME ASSESSMENT**

The Programme Assessment is a critical element in the development of a Security Risk Assessment (SRA). To ensure an accurate and realistic SRA, it is imperative that the team understand the anticipated needs, requirements and operating parameters of the United Nations agencies, programmes, funds and organizations expected to operate in the country, region or area. Programme managers are experts in this regard and examples of required information are listed in the non-exhaustive list of questions below. Other pertinent information should be added as appropriate.

1. Agency and types of programmes and/or projects to be conducted (e.g., WHO, malaria eradication programme and polio monitoring programme).
2. What are the major outcomes expected from these programmes/projects (i.e., 80% reduction in malaria within six months)?
3. Location of offices.
4. How many international staff and national staff will be required (and are already in place) at each location?
5. What are the operating locations/areas of those programmes and projects, including general areas or approximate distances from major towns?
6. Likely timeframe before deploying staff and establishing offices, noting that office security arrangements and full MOSS implementation will be required prior to commencing operations.
7. Which INGOs or other organizations are likely to be implementing partners, if any?
8. Are the programmes considered to be 'humanitarian' or 'development'?
9. Are there other means or options for programme delivery or other means of achieving the desired results that do not require the physical presence of UN system staff in the area of conflict?
10. Will the presence of the programmes and staff (e.g., offices, vehicles, etc.) be a stabilizing factor in the area?
11. What is the expected, overall impact of these programmes and projects?

EXAMPLES OF SECURITY RISK ASSESSMENTS IN THE FIELD

The following examples indicate the flexibility of the security risk management process to undertake an SRA at three different levels. These tables summarize the process.

- Example 1 – ‘UN House’

Activity: UN House Office survey

Assets: Staff, building, vehicles, computers, office equipment, sensitive documents.

Threats	Vulnerabilities	Likelihood	Mitigating	Impact	RISK
Major fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timber construction • No effective fire service • Poor electrical wiring • Unenthusiastic staff • No fire alarm system • High density staff numbers in building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Likely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good and recent training of all staff • All fire exits marked and refurbished • Fire extinguishers available & serviced. • Good evacuation plan, recently tested • No smoking policy • Kitchen in outside building • Good concentration points • Full back up of files weekly • Smoke detectors installed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Injury to staff • Destruction of building • Destruction of computers and other equipment • Loss of vehicles • Destruction of VHF antennae • Cessation of UN operations 	<p>LOW to MODERATE</p> <p>(Acceptable)</p>
Car/Truck Bombing	•	•	•	•	
Office Invasion	•	•	•	•	
	•	•	•	•	

- Example 2 – ‘A road mission’

Activity: Road Mission in hazardous location

Assets: 4 x Staff, 1 x vehicle

Threats	Vulnerabilities	Likelihood	Mitigating	Impact	RISK
Ambush	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Light-skinned vehicle • One route to destination • Precedent of ambush on route • Poor UN liaison with groups • Poor road (slow travel) • Must travel by day (easily seen) • No body armour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Likely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4x4 vehicles (off road capability) • Will take guide from the region • UN not previously attacked 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Death or injury to staff • Loss of vehicles 	<p>HIGH to CRITICAL</p> <p>(Unacceptable)</p>
Serious Accident	•	•	•	•	
Hi-jacking	•	•	•	•	
Break-down	•	•	•	•	
	•	•	•	•	

• Example 3 – Country Level

This example is provided in a condensed/abbreviated version assessment. This format may be used when presenting findings to an SMT or other group.

Activity: Country Assessment
Assets: Staff, Equipment, Properties and Programmes

Threat Assessment		Programme Assessment	Vulnerability Assessment		Risk Analysis	
Threats	Situation Analysis		UN Weaknesses	UN Strengths	Impact	Likelihood
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active terrorists within the region • Organised and armed criminal groups present • Easy access to guns and munitions • Frustrated and marginalised civil groups • Landmines and UXOs common • Roadside ambush has occurred against UN and NGO vehicles • 'Rebels' have mortar weapons and heavy machine guns • Kidnapping for ransom is on the rise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New, replaced government that is fragile • Religious and ethnic extremism rife • Tensions high of access to water resources in north and south • Police under-trained and poorly paid. • Corruption rife in new government • Failing economy and few natural resources • Anti-government conflict in two of three bordering countries • Medical facilities poor • Roads and transport infrastructure in ruins • Agriculture based on subsistence farming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UN programmes critical to feed starving communities and to address dysentery and polio epidemics • Political collapse likely to ignite deflagration of the region • Terrorist groups seek to overthrow current government and install fundamental religious laws and councils • Government is UN member and has requested assistance – GA agrees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UN respected and supported by <u>some</u> governments in the region • UN GA to establish a political mission • New DO and security team • Electoral support mission is a high priority (i.e., mvmt over wide locations) • No DPKO troops and other State troops likely within six months • Rebels have history of being a target with impunity • UN Staff are seen to have a monetary and political value • Explosives readily available • Programmes typically outside the capital and require mvmt by road • No helicopters available • Constant storms cause gaps in radio comms • Enhancements to MOSS for terrorist attack not in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure compounds with basic MOSS compliance and professional protective guards • Training provided to all staff entering the country • Armed escorts avail for UN missions • Careful planning of missions, including changing of routes, accommodation, etc. • Armoured SUV vehicles available • Ceiling staff numbers strictly enforced • Use of third parties to implement programmes • On-going information gathering and analysis capability being developed • Country-wide UN comms system 	<p><u>Terror Attack</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Death or injury to staff • Withdrawal of most UN staff • Cancellation or delays to programmes • Loss of assets • Death or disability to local communities • Increased chance of civil war and regional deflagration <p><u>Other attacks:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays to programmes • Loss of assets • Loss of morale • Use of funds for added security measures • Increase in resources, including staff time, to security matters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very likely • Very likely
					Level of Risk = High Unacceptable	

Notes on the above example: Many issues raised in the Threat Assessment will impact on information in the Vulnerability Assessment and Programme Assessments and vice-versa.

For example:

1. 'Under-trained police' may link to provision of 'armed escorts' – is it police escorts? Are they from one ethnic/political/religious group? or,
2. 'Terrorist groups in region'....' + Fragile government '..... + 'no MOSS in place'.... + 'UN support to Government' = risk!

Conclusion: Based on the above threats, vulnerabilities and risk considerations, the level of risk would be 'unacceptable'. Therefore, options to reduce the risk are required. This will be done through an increase in mitigation measures to reduce: (1) the vulnerabilities; (2) the likelihood of the event impacting on the organization; and (3) the impact on staff and programmes if the event/incident does occur. In doing so, the risk will be reduced to an acceptable level....within a specified security environment.

Determination of the security phase after implementing the mitigating measure will include political and operating considerations, and in this case is likely to be security phase 3 or 4. It must be noted that security phases are not simply a direct reflection of the risk, or just the threat – the security phase itself is a mitigating measure in terms of introducing Minimum Operating Security Standards (MOSS) which include standard and mandatory regulations, procedures and equipment.